

Study of Oxidative Free Radical Damage and the Status of Vitamin-C in Atopic Dermatitis Patient

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Abstract:

Background: Atopic dermatitis (AD) is a chronic inflammatory skin condition characterized by oxidative stress and free radical damage. This study aims to investigate the oxidative stress marker, serum malondialdehyde (MDA), and the antioxidant status of vitamin C in patients with atopic dermatitis.

Materials and Methods: This cross-sectional control study was conducted in the Department of Biochemistry in collaboration with the Department of Dermatology at Burdwan Medical College and Hospital. The study was conducted over 18 months, from July 2019 to January 2021. A total of 50 AD patients (Group A) and 40 age- and sex-matched healthy volunteers (Group B) were recruited. Inclusion criteria involved AD patients diagnosed by suitable criteria, while exclusion criteria included conditions or habits that could affect oxidative stress or vitamin C levels. Serum malondialdehyde (MDA) and vitamin C levels were measured using colorimetric and ELISA methods, respectively. Statistical analysis was performed using Student's t-test and chi-square tests to determine significance.

Results: The study found no significant difference in the age and sex distribution between the case and control groups. In Group A, 68% of patients were female, and a mixed diet was the most common dietary habit (76%). Family history was positive in 24% of cases, while 32% reported sun allergy. The mean serum vitamin C level was significantly lower in the case group (0.846 ± 0.1 mg/dl) compared to the control group (0.918 ± 0.04 mg/dl, $p=0.005$). Conversely, the mean serum MDA level was significantly higher in the case group (4.429 ± 0.04 nmol/ml) than in the control group (3.432 ± 0.13 nmol/ml, $p=0.01$). A negative correlation was observed between MDA and vitamin C levels in the case group (correlation factor = -0.467 , $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: The findings indicate that atopic dermatitis is associated with increased oxidative stress and decreased antioxidant status, as evidenced by elevated MDA and reduced vitamin C levels. The negative correlation between MDA and vitamin C suggests that oxidative stress plays a significant role in the pathophysiology of AD, highlighting the potential benefit of antioxidant therapy in managing this condition.

Keywords: Atopic dermatitis, oxidative stress, malondialdehyde (MDA), vitamin C, free radical damage.

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Introduction

Atopic dermatitis (AD), also known as atopic eczema, is a chronic or chronically recurring inflammatory skin disease, which continues to increase in prevalence. It affects every generation, from infancy (15–20 %) to adulthood (1–3%). It is clinically characterized by dry skin and itchy papules (sometimes vesicles in infants) that get excoriated and lichenified, sometimes crusting. AD has a multidimensional burden, including a

profound impact on the quality-of-life of patients and their families. The pathogenesis of AD is characterized by a complex relationship between genetic, immunological and environmental aspects [1].

Genetic factors can be classified in two groups: The first group includes mutations of genes encoding for structural epidermal proteins or involved in the maintenance of epidermal barrier function. The

second group includes genes involved in the regulation of immune response. Chronic skin inflammation is associated with reactive oxygen species (ROS) overproduction, such as superoxide (O_2^-) and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2).

Exogenous factors, such as solar radiation or pollution, and/or psychological processes may also increase ROS concentration. Over time, accumulation of ROS eventually exceeds the defence capacity of the antioxidant system (AOS). This condition, defined as oxidative stress (OS), plays a role in the pathogenesis of AD, as well as in other cutaneous and non-cutaneous diseases [2].

AOS components include enzymes such as superoxide dismutase, superoxide reductase, catalase, peroxiredoxins and thioredoxin, as well as exogenous and endogenous non-enzymatic molecules such as vitamins A, C, and E, uric acid, coenzyme Q10. The entire glutathione system consisting of glutathione (GSH) and glutathione reductase, glutathione peroxidase enzymes. [3]. The direct impact of ROS in biological systems, i.e., modification of DNA, lipids, and proteins, can be evaluated through measurement of different biomarkers.

Vitamin C (ascorbic acid) plays an important role in preserving skin health and can encourage the differentiation of keratinocytes, decrease melanin synthesis, contributing to antioxidant defence against UV-induced photodamage. Normal skin requires high levels of vitamin C, which plays varied roles in the skin including skin barrier and collagen production in the dermis, ability to resist skin oxidation, cell signal pathways regulating cell growth and differentiation.

There is also a concentration gradient of ascorbic acid in the epidermal keratinocytes [4,5].

Materials & Methods:

Study area: Department of Biochemistry, in collaboration with the department of Dermatology, Burdwan Medical College and Hospital, Burdwan.

Study design: A cross-sectional control study

Study period: One and half year (July 2019 to January 2021)

Study population:

Group A-(50- Cases) Atopic dermatitis patients attending Dermatology outpatient department, Burdwan medical college and hospital, Burdwan.

Group B-(40- Cases) Healthy volunteers, randomly selected from relatives, friends or persons accompanying patients.

Sample size:

- Group- A -50= Cases group
- Group-B - 40= Controls group

Inclusion criteria for cases- Atopic dermatitis patients diagnosed by suitable criteria **and for controls-** healthy age and sex-matched subjects

Exclusion criteria: Unusual dietary habits, acute or chronic infections, oral supplements or drugs-containing vitamin C, alcoholism, illicit drug use, anorexia nervosa, Crohn's disease Coeliac disease, haemodialysis, cancer chemotherapy, smoking, exposure to industrial chemicals, pesticides, chronic diseases.

Parameters to be studied: Serum malondialdehyde. (Test done by Colorimeter- TBA method) and serum vitamin C. (Test done by Elisa Reader)

Study tools: Predesigned pretested method of assessment of Serum malondialdehyde and vitamin C.. Blood samples from each subject to determine the above parameters.

Study techniques: Proper counselling and informed consent from each subject (or from guardian, in case of minor), selected in the study population Detailed history and clinical examination.

Methodology: Random blood sample were collected from patients after taking informed consent. Blood for estimation of serum malondialdehyde and Vitamin C was collected in plain vials after 10 minutes of rest through aseptic technique and without using tourniquet. For vitamin C vial was wrapped immediately after collecting the blood with a brown colour paper / aluminium foil to prevent degradation.

Statistical analysis: Comparison of all the variables was done using students' T-test and chi square test. The results in each parameter under study was graded as follows: Non-significant- $P > 0.05$; significant- $P < 0.05$; highly significant $P < 0.001$.

Results & Analysis:

Table 1: Age Distribution among Case & Control Group

Age in Years	Case (Group-A) n=50		Control (Group-B) n=40	
	No	%	No	%
12 – 25	28	56.0	22	55.0
26 – 40	14	28.0	15	37.5

41 – 50	08	16.0	03	7.5
Total	50	100.0	40	100
Mean & SD	27.020±8.57		24.825±7.89	
p Value	0.132(NS)			

Table 2: Age and Sex Distribution among case and control group.

Age in Years	Case (Group-A) n=50				Control (Group-B) n=40			
	Male	%	Female	%	Male	%	Female	%
12 – 25	09	18.0	19	38.0	07	17.5	15	37.5
26 – 40	05	10.0	09	18.0	08	20.0	07	17.5
41 – 50	02	04.0	06	12.0	01	2.5	02	5.0
Total	16	32.0	34	68.0	16	40.0	24	60.0
P Value	Chi-Square- 4.187 p Value- 0.65							

Table 3: Demographic characteristics of Case group (n=50)

Demographic characteristics		No of Cases	Percentage
Family History	Yes	12	24
	No	38	76
Allergy	Sun	16	32
	Dust	10	20
	Woollen cloths	08	16
	No	16	32
Food habit	Vegetarian	12	24
	Mixed diet	38	76

Table 4: Mean & SD value of Vitamin-C among case and control group.

Vitamin -C (mg/dl)	Mean	SD	p Value
Case	0.846	±0.1	0.005(HS)
Control	0.918	±0.04	

Table 5: Mean & SD value of Serum MDA among case and control group.

Serum MDA (n mol./ml)	Mean	SD	p Value
Case	4.429	±0.04	0.01(HS)
Control	3.432	±0.13	

Table 6: Correlation between MDA vs Vitamin –C in Case Group

Correlation between MDA vs Vitamin-C		
MDA	Vitamin- C	
	Correlation factor	p. Value
	-0.467	<0.001

Figure 6: Correlation between MDA vs Vitamin –C in Case Group.

Serum MDA level is negatively correlated with Vitamin C level with significant difference (p value= <0.001).

Discussion

The present study was conducted in the department of Biochemistry, in collaboration with the department of Dermatology of Burdwan Medical College and Hospital, Burdwan. 50 consecutive cases of Atopic dermatitis attending Dermatology outpatient department, Burdwan medical college and hospital, Burdwan during the study period of July 2019 to January 2021 were selected as study population. 40 healthy age and gender matched healthy volunteers randomly selected from relatives; friends or persons accompanying patients were selected as control.

The present study aimed to assess if there is any difference in free radical status, antioxidant status indicated by serum Vitamin-C level, in atopic dermatitis cases as compared to control. The present study also aimed to find out association of free radical status with atopic dermatitis and antioxidant status in atopic dermatitis.

In the present study the mean age of case and control group was 27.12 and 24.82 years respectively with no statistically significant difference between two groups (p value= 0.132). We observed females are more prone to atopic dermatitis compared to males. Regarding sex distribution two groups were comparable (p value= 0.65).

While analysing the mean Vitamin C level in case and control group we found it was 0.846±0.1 mg/dl and 0.918±0.04 mg/dl respectively. Serum vitamin C level was significantly higher in control group compared to case group (p value= 0.005).

Atopic dermatitis (AD) is a chronic relapsing inflammation of the skin associated with allergies. The lesions are characterized by erythematous papules with itching or scaling, affecting 15–30% of children (Bieber, 2008; Kim et al., 2013; Tollefson and Bruckner, 2014) [6-8]. One reason this is important is the structural or functional damage of the skin barrier (Sivaranjani, 2013; Zaniboni et al., 2016) [9,10]. Keratinocytes and their intercellular lipids are important components of the human skin barrier, and vitamin C can promote keratinocyte differentiation and the production of interstitial material (Savini et al., 2002; Kim et al., 2011) [11,12]. As the most abundant lipid in the skin barrier material, ceramide is generated at the end of keratinocyte differentiation (Uchida et al., 2001) [13]. AD patients lack several nutrients, including vitamin A and vitamin C. A greater number of food allergens have shown an association with an increase in the number of deficient nutrients (Gorman et al., 2007)

[14]. The ratio of vitamin C intake is significantly higher in more than three restricted groups compared to the non-restricted group, which demonstrates that vitamin C can improve chronic inflammation and positively influence AD and that the intake of several foods containing high levels of vitamin C and vitamin A may be related to a decrease in the risk of AD and asthma diseases (Lim et al., 2013; Park and Zippin, 2014) [15,16]. Vitamin C can stimulate ceramide production in keratinocytes and improve overall epidermal barrier function (Kim K.P. et al., 2015) [17]. With increases in clinical symptoms of AD, vitamin C and ceramide levels were reduced, which demonstrated that vitamin C and ceramide levels and the severity of AD are positively correlated (Shin et al., 2016) [18].

Although vitamin C can be an adjuvant treatment for a variety of dermatitis, oral vitamin C still causes symmetrical AD (Assier et al., 2013) [19].

Recent studies have begun to provide more detailed information as to specific functional implications for suboptimal vitamin C status in inflamed skin lesions. One notable study has reported significantly compromised vitamin C status in patients with atopic dermatitis, with plasma levels ranging between 6 and 31 mol/L (optimal healthy levels > 60 M), and an inverse relationship between plasma vitamin C and total ceramide levels in the epidermis of the affected individuals [18].

The mean serum malondialdehyde (MDA) level in case and control group was 4.429±0.04 n.mol/ml and 3.432±0.13.05 n. mol/ml respectively. Serum malondialdehyde (MDA) level was significantly higher in case group compared to control group (p value= 0.01). While analysing the correlation between serum MDA and Vitamin C level among the study subjects of case group it shows that serum MDA level is negatively correlated with Vitamin C level with significant difference (p value= <0.001).

MDA was the most frequently measured marker of oxidative stress, in different types of samples. Compared to those found in healthy controls, serum levels of MDA of AD patients were significantly higher in studies by Amin M.N. et al and Sivaranjani Net al; [20,21] and not significantly different in studies by Uysal P et al and Chung et al [22,23]. Urinary MDA was evaluated in study by Nakai K et al [24] and, although the difference between patients and controls was not significant, a correlation was observed between MDA levels and AD severity and extent. In exhaled breath condensates, the median levels of MDA were lower in AD patients than controls, with a difference close to statistical significance in study by Peroni D.G et al [25].

The pathology underlying the condition of atopic dermatitis is complex and involves activation of

auto-immune or allergic inflammation with associated generation of cytokines and cellular dysfunction, and consequent breakdown of the skin epidermal lipid barrier. Treatments are therefore targeted at both the underlying inflammation and the repair and maintenance of the epidermal structures. Nutrition plays an integral part in both these aspects and numerous studies have investigated the impact of dietary manipulation for alleviation of acute and chronic skin pathologies, although firm conclusions as to efficacy remain elusive. Vitamin C is often used in anti-inflammatory formulations or as a component of nutrition studies but its individual efficacy has not been investigated.

Conclusion

Vitamin C status has been reported to be compromised in individuals with atopic dermatitis, with lower levels measured compared with unaffected individuals. This may reflect increased turnover of the redox-labile vitamin C, as is seen in many inflammatory conditions. Recent studies have begun to provide more detailed information as to specific functional implications for suboptimal vitamin C status in inflamed skin lesions like atopic dermatitis. We observed a significantly compromised vitamin C status in patients with atopic dermatitis compared with unaffected individuals, and an inverse relationship between plasma vitamin C and serum malondialdehyde (MDA) levels in the epidermis of the affected individuals.

References

- Peng, W.; Novak, N. Pathogenesis of atopic dermatitis. *Clin. Exp. Allergy* 2015, 45, 566–574.
- Cannavò, S.P.; Tonacci, A.; Bertino, L.; Casciaro, M.; Borgia, F.; Gangemi, S. The role of oxidative stress in the biology of melanoma: A systematic review. *Pathol. Res. Pract.* 2019, 215, 21–28.
- Bickers, D.R.; Athar, M. Oxidative stress in the pathogenesis of skin disease. *J. Investig. Dermatol.* 2006, 126, 2565–2575.
- Shindo Y., Witt E., Han D., Epstein W., Packer L. (1994). Enzymic and non-enzymic antioxidants in epidermis and dermis of human skin. *J. Invest. Dermatol.* 102 122–124. 10.1111/1523-1747.ep12371744.
- Weaver B. A. (2009). Herpes zoster overview: natural history and incidence. *J. Am. Osteopath. Assoc.* 109(6 Suppl. 2), S2–S6.
- Bieber, T. (2008). Atopic dermatitis. *N. Engl. J. Med.* 358, 1483–1494.
- Kim, J., Kwon, J., Noh, G., and Lee, S. S. (2013). The effects of elimination diet on nutritional status in subjects with atopic dermatitis. *Nutr. Res. Pract.* 7, 488–494.
- Tollefson, M. M., and Bruckner, A. L. (2014). Atopic dermatitis: skin-directed management. *Pediatrics* 134, e1735–e1744.
- Sivaranjani, N. (2013). Role of reactive oxygen species and antioxidants in atopic dermatitis. *J. Clin. Diagn. Res.* 7, 2683–2685.
- Zaniboni, M. C., Samorano, L. P., Orfali, R. L., and Aoki, V. (2016). Skin barrier in atopic dermatitis: beyond filaggrin. *An. Bras. Dermatol.* 91, 472–478.
- Savini, I., et al. (2002). Characterization of keratinocyte differentiation induced by ascorbic acid: protein kinase C involvement and vitamin C homeostasis. *J. Invest. Dermatol.* 118, 372–379.
- Kim, J., Yun, H., and Cho, Y. (2011). Analysis of ceramide metabolites in differentiating epidermal keratinocytes treated with calcium or vitamin C. *Nutr. Res. Pract.* 5, 396–403.
- Uchida, Y., Behne, M., Quiec, D., Elias, P. M., and Holleran, W. M. (2001). Vitamin C stimulates sphingolipid production and markers of barrier formation in submerged human keratinocyte cultures. *J. Invest. Dermatol.* 117, 1307–1313.
- Gorman, N., Zaharia, A., Trask, H. S., Szakacs, J. G., Jacobs, N. J., Jacobs, J. M., et al. (2007). Effect of iron and ascorbate on uroporphyrin in ascorbate-requiring mice as a model for porphyria cutanea tarda. *Hepatology* 45, 187–194.
- Lim, H., Song, K., Kim, R., Sim, J., Park, E., Ahn, K., et al. (2013). Nutrient intake, and food restriction in children with atopic dermatitis. *Clin. Nutr. Res.* 2, 52–58.
- Park, M. E., and Zippin, J. H. (2014). Allergic contact dermatitis to cosmetics. *Dermatol. Clin.* 32, 1–11.
- Kim, K., Bae, O. N., Koh, S. H., Kang, S., Lim, K. M., Noh, J. Y., et al. (2015). High-dose vitamin C injection to cancer patients may promote thrombosis through procoagulant activation of erythrocytes. *Toxicol. Sci.* 147, 350–359.
- Shin, J., Kim, Y. J., Kwon, O., Kim, N. I., and Cho, Y. (2016). Associations among plasma vitamin C, epidermal ceramide and clinical severity of atopic dermatitis. *Nutr. Res. Pract.* 10, 398–403.
- Assier, H., Wolkenstein, P., Grille, C., and Chosidow, O. (2013). Contact dermatitis caused by ascorbyl tetraisopalmitate in a cream used for the management of atopic dermatitis. *Clin. Nutr. Res.* 2, 52–58.
- Amin M. N., Liza K. F., Sarwar M. S., et al. Effect of lipid peroxidation, antioxidants, macro minerals and trace elements on eczema. *Archives of Dermatological Research* . 2015;307(7):617–623.

21. Sivaranjani, N. (2013). Role of reactive oxygen species and antioxidants in atopic dermatitis. *J. Clin. Diagn. Res.* 7, 2683–2685.
22. Chung J., Oh S.-Y., Shin Y.-K. Association of glutathione-S-transferase polymorphisms with atopic dermatitis risk in preschool age children. *Clinical Chemistry and Laboratory Medicine.* 2009;47(12):1475–1481.
23. Uysal, P.; Avcil, S.; Abas, B. I.; Yenisey, Ç. Evaluation of oxidant–antioxidant balance in children with atopic dermatitis: A case-control study. *Am. J. Clin. Dermatol.* 2016, 17, 527–537
24. Nakai K., Yoneda K., Maeda R., et al. Urinary biomarker of oxidative stress in patients with psoriasis vulgaris and atopic dermatitis. *Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology.* 2009;23(12):1405–1408.
25. Peroni, D.G.; Bodini, A.; Corradi, M.; Coghi, A.; Boner, A.L.; Piacentini, G.L. Markers of oxidative stress are increased in exhaled breath condensates of children with atopic dermatitis. *Br. J. Dermatol.* 2012, 166, 839–843.